

EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT. EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT METHODS AND DECISIONS

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ABSTRACT

At present, as in all areas of our republic, major reforms are being implemented in education. The article describes modern methods of education management, management functions and forms based on foreign and local research.

INTRODUCTION

Since education is the foundation of the country's economic and spiritual development, it is always in the focus of attention on the basis of new principles in the humanization of social structures, the laws of the market economy, changes in ideological and moral principles, unemployment, material shortage, lack of control of children, separation of families. is the basis for the development of measures and activities aimed at finding a solution. In this case, first of all, children and then adults need social support. In such conditions, there was a demand for a social pedagogue as a specialist who solves pedagogical issues related to the social problems of the society and helps the individual in the process of his socialization.

The strength of any country is determined by the spiritual maturity and intellectual potential of its citizens. The spiritual maturity and intellectual potential of citizens is the content of the educational system, the existence of material and spiritual conditions that serve for the comprehensive formation of a person, the level of a healthy social environment in society, the content of social relations, as well as the ethno-psychological characteristics of the population. are formed on the basis of characteristics, moral views and life beliefs. Education and training is an integral part of any society, an indicator of its culture and the basis of its development. It ensures the unity and succession of social experience, spiritual-ethical and cultural traditions, as well as the development of society. This program is a modern system of education and training management and the main principles and features of its management. The purpose and tasks of preschool education management by preschool education, the task of preschool education and education management, management methods, forms, principles,

laws, as well as, attention is paid to the principles of organizing preschool education organizations of different types and to the scientific-theoretical approach to it.

From this point of view, it is important to study the theoretical foundations of the development of media competence among the leaders of higher education institutions and develop practical suggestions.

The emergence and development of educational management has a long history, but the theory of management began to develop only at the beginning of the 20th century. "Management" is taken from the English word and translated into Uzbek in the sense of organization of management, leadership. In the general plan, management means management, that is, organization and management of one or another type of activity (organization and management) in the economic, financial and other business spheres of human life. In the United States at the beginning of the 20th century, there were favorable conditions in which the evolution of scientific management schools began. A huge labor market has appeared in a democratic country. The existence of education has helped many intelligent people to show their qualities. New methods of leadership were required. In 1911, Frederick Taylor's book *The Principles* laid the foundation for research in the new discipline of leadership. He proved that group influence can change people's attitude to work.

A manager must have knowledge of various fields and apply proven methods. The school has solved a number of important management problems that arise everywhere in large-scale industrial production. The most important task in management is to work with people. The given descriptions of management indicate that while it means management, the economy of administrative command is fundamentally different from management. These differences are as follows: The first difference is related to the market economy, and administrative command is not a system of conducting the economy based on a plan.

The second difference comes from the first difference, that is, in developed countries, management is a method of economic management.

The third difference - the difference between management and the management of a socialist system can be determined based on the combination of the last four descriptions. It can be said that "management is the science and art of effective management." Such management is realized due to the high qualification of those engaged in such work, i.e. managers, their knowledge, active creative work, initiative, flexibility of thinking, ability to solve tactical and strategic issues, ability to work directly with people. In the Oxford annotated dictionary, the description of management is expressed by the following simple word. It says "Management is a special skill and knowledge in performing administrative work."

In the current era, the various requirements for management, i.e. the work method, the ability to conduct work, the art and science of correctly directing the movement of people in joint activities, are defined without strict administrative requirements. reflects the fulfillment of the goal.

In addition to the above qualities, it is appropriate to mention 2 characteristics of modern management in developed countries:

1- Orientation of the activities of the management corps to obtain high-quality products that meet consumer demand (marketing approach in management).

2- Orientation of the manager's work to increase the well-being of the team members of the organization (humanization of management activities).

As a result, the term "Management" has one more, or rather two common meanings. It is used to refer to the entire organization's management team or top management corps in the sense of gathering more. In such meanings, the word "Manager" is usually used when there is a certain contrast between 2 types of activities: managers (managers) and producers (workers).

Laws of educational management reflect the objectively existing, recurring interactions of various elements and events in the management process. They are divided into public and private. General laws are characteristic of all management systems, while private ones are related to the implementation of some educational organizations and institutions.

The following can be included among the general principles of management: priority efficiency and conscious planned management; to strengthen the processes of the interaction of the controlling and controlled systems, the subject and the object of control, division of labor and cooperation in management. We will consider these laws.

The priority effectiveness of the conscious management of education is legitimate, because the planned management system of the processes taking place in it is actually more effective than the management systems that regulate these processes involuntarily. This is evidenced by the widespread use of program-targeted approach, systematic approach and analysis at all levels of management in current education.

The fact that the relationship between the controlling and controlled systems, the subject and the object of control is legal means the compliance of the control field with the requirements of the control object. For example, changes in the development of the economy in the mid-1990s required a specific change in the entire management apparatus in our country, which was reflected in the set of reforms in education and personnel training that began in 1997. As a result, the system of education and its management acquired the principle of sustainable development in accordance with the requirements of socio-economic, political changes, scientific and technical development.

The division of labor and the strengthening of cooperation processes in management can also be included in the general laws of education management. Legitimacy, first of all, reflects the horizontal and vertical division of labor in management, which is due to the development of management, the expansion of the scope of managed systems, the emergence of new functions and types of activities. Secondly, the division of labor requires its coordination, that is, the coordination of the work of management subjects, which is expressed in the cooperation of management labor.

If general laws are specific to management as a whole, private laws are specific to certain aspects and systems of management.

The following can be included among the private laws: the change of management functions, the optimization of the number of management stages, the concentration of management functions, and the law of widespread control.

The laws of change of educational management functions indicate the rise of one function and the decline of another at different hierarchical levels of management. For example, if at the level of the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, strategic tasks covering the content of education (curriculums, programs, state education standards, textbooks, study guides, etc.) are solved, then At the level of the educational institution, tactical issues related to the implementation of more general secondary education goals are addressed.

The rules of optimizing the number of management stages require the elimination of redundant management links, which increases its flexibility and speed.

Consolidation of educational management functions means that each level of management tends to concentrate more functions, that is, to increase the number of management personnel. Information about the increasing number of bureaucratic apparatuses in all countries clearly demonstrates this law.

The distribution of control reflects the relationship between the number of employees under his control and the ability of the manager to effectively lead their activities and control their work.

The laws of education management (both general and private) have an objective nature and are implemented in the process of managing people's activities. When formulating the principles of educational management, the laws of management should be fully taken into account

The following can be included among the general principles of educational management: clear goal orientation, planning, knowledge, discipline, motivation, hierarchy (graduality).

The principle of clear goal-orientation is defined by the essence of program-targeted management, which provides for the clear setting of goals for each educational management body and each of its divisions. In this case, the goal should be really achievable and as clearly defined as possible, which ensures that the work is reasonable and mobilizes the efforts of employees for its implementation.

The principle of clear goal orientation implies not only the set goals, but also the determination of the ratio of these goals to the necessary resources. This requires not only ensuring that the goals are linked to the key resources needed to achieve them, but also focusing on the weakest link that prevents the achievement of the goals.

The principle of planned management of education is also related to program-targeted management and envisages the creation of an action program and its implementation. Planning is manifested in the normalization of work conditions and its distribution among performers, coordination and guidance of performers' actions, as well as organization of accounting and control of the execution of each job and the program as a whole. The implementation of this principle leads to the organization of the entire management system based on the plan[11].

The principle of knowledge means that the manager knows the object of management, at least, is able to accept the useful advice of experts when making decisions. The principle of knowledge is related to the horizontal division of labor by functions.

Discipline, which must be present at any level in any management system, is an indispensable principle of management. Discipline provides for the unquestionable execution of the leader's instructions, duties, instructions, orders and other directive documents. The level of discipline largely determines the management culture.

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